

Words with O “Infixes” in the Uzbek Language

Nodirbek Nosirjon o‘g‘li Xabibillayev ¹

¹ Namangan State Pedagogical Institute, Department of Language Teaching Methods, Lecturer

Abstract:

In Uzbek linguistics, there are several groups of words that are difficult to classify. One of them is words with "infix". In this article, such a group of words is divided into groups. Through this article, the author addressed the almost untouched topic in linguistics and expressed his opinion on the existing problem in this field.

Keywords: Infix, morpheme, dictionary, word formation, possessive word, prefix, suffix, noun formation, adjective formation, lexeme, compound word.

INTRODUCTION

Several practical measures taken in the field of the state language are currently showing positive results. For example, the reforms being carried out regarding the digitization of the language can serve as evidence of this. While such effective reforms are being implemented in the field of language, the presence of certain unresolved issues in Uzbek grammar indicates that new research is still awaiting attention. One of the issues expected to be resolved is the words with the "infix" "o". Below are considerations related to this issue.

LITERATURE REVIEW AND METHODOLOGY

The reason these words are named as such is that they entered the Uzbek language through Russian, where "o" is considered an infix that appears in the middle of a word. This is distinguished as a separate morpheme. In Russian, the function of this infix is to connect two lexemes. Such words have entered from foreign languages in their original form. Previous studies have not delved into this phenomenon in detail, meaning this issue has not been previously addressed. In Professor Ayub G‘ulomov’s "Morpheme Dictionary of the Uzbek Language," words containing the "o" infix are segmented into components such as ion/o/gen/lar and shlak/o/blok. Words of this nature are segmented in nearly the same manner in the book. However, the words anarx/o-sindikal/izm and anarx/o-sindikal/ist are segmented differently. What the scholar intended with this is unclear to us. If we pay attention to the segmentation of other words in this book, it is not difficult to see that these words were prepared based on Uzbek grammar influenced by Russian grammar. That is,

during that period, Uzbek grammar was created under the influence of Russian grammar, and it is no secret today that many aspects of Uzbek linguistics were concluded based on the characteristics of the Russian language. Later, in the textbook on morphology, word formation, and morphonology titled "Contemporary Uzbek Literary Language," prepared by Professor Abduvali Berdialiyev and Ixtiyor Ermatov, although there are no such words, it is noted that the word *kungaboqar*, which comes between two bases and connects them, belongs to the lexical-syntactic method of diachronic word formation. We believe this definition is correct. The reason is that the "o" in words of this nature does not serve to connect two lexemes in the Uzbek language. Additionally, even if it did serve to connect them, it would be considered a historical word combination and viewed as simplified today. In general, if loanwords are segmented based on the characteristics of the language they originated from, it will significantly negatively impact the development of segmentation of words not only in Uzbek but also in other languages. Consider this: if words borrowed from Russian are segmented based on Russian rules, words borrowed from Arabic are segmented based on Arabic rules, and words borrowed from Persian are segmented based on Persian rules, the process will become quite complicated and may ultimately lead to absurdity. Therefore, when segmenting loanwords, relying on a single principle in Uzbek regarding the separation into bases and affixes will simplify the situation. That is, the part considered a base must convey an independent lexical meaning. The part considered an affix must be able to attach to other words and contribute its specific grammatical and lexical meanings. Only then can we say that a clear system of segmentation will function. Thus, from the above analysis, it becomes clear that the "o" in such words is not segmented in Uzbek. Therefore, we will examine such words one by one.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The "o" infix in words can appear in the following positions:

- ✓ Between lexemes;
- ✓ Between a morpheme and a lexeme;
- ✓ Within borrowed compound words where one part is not used independently.

1. The o "infix" between lexemes.

- In the word *aero/ionotherapy*, we previously discussed the part "aero-". "Ion" is a chemical substance and an independent word in Uzbek. "Therapy" is also a lexeme related to medicine.
- In the word *basidiospora/lar*, the part "basidia" can be used independently in Uzbek and is a biological term. "Spore" is also a biological term and can be used independently in Uzbek. The "-lar" suffix in this word indicates plurality.
- In the word *dactylograph/ic*, the part "dactyl" in Uzbek refers to meanings such as actions performed using fingers or gestures. "Graph" is a borrowed word meaning "to write." The "-ic" morpheme in this word serves to form an adjective. The word *dactylograph/y* has a similar structure, but the "-y" morpheme serves to form a noun.
- In the word *dialectograph/y*, the lexeme "dialect" in Uzbek means dialect or accent. We have already discussed the "graph" part. The "-y" morpheme in this word serves to form a noun.
- In the word *climatograph/ic*, the part "climate" is a borrowed word and is used independently in Uzbek to mean climate. We have already discussed the independent use of the "graph" part. In this word, the "-ic" morpheme serves to form an adjective. The word *climatograph/y* has a similar structure, with the "-y" morpheme serving to form a noun.
- In the word *lexicograph/ic*, the word "lexic" can be used independently in Uzbek and means related to the vocabulary of a language. We have already discussed the "graph" part. The "-ic"

morpheme in this word serves to form an adjective. The structure of lexicograph/y is similar to this word, with the "-y" morpheme serving to form a noun.

- In the word magnetobiology, the part "magnet" can be used independently in Uzbek and refers to a solid object that can attract iron and steel items. The part "biology" can also be used independently in Uzbek. The "-y" morpheme in this word serves to form a noun.
- In the word magnetoelastic/ic, the two lexemes "magnet" and "elastic" are words that have independent meanings in Uzbek. The "-ic" morpheme in this compound word serves to form an adjective. The structure of magnetoelectric/ic is similar to this word, where the second lexeme is "electric."

The words magnitograf/ik and magnitograf/iya consist of two lexemes, which we discussed in detail earlier. In these words, the morpheme -ik functions to form an adjective, while -iya serves to form a noun.

In the word magnitometr/ik, the two lexemes are "magnet" and "meter." The morpheme -ik in this word forms an adjective. The structure of magnitometr/iya is similar, with the morpheme -iya serving to form a noun.

In the word metallofizik/a, the two lexemes are "metal" and "physic," and the -a morpheme forms a noun. Words like metallofon/lar, metallograf/ik, metallograf/iya, metallokeramik/a, metallooptik/a, metalloorgan/ik, and metalloprotein/lar all have "metal" as their first lexeme. The second lexemes are "phone," "graph," "ceramic," "optic," "organ," and "protein," respectively. The morpheme -lar adds plurality, -ik forms adjectives, and -iya and -a form nouns.

In the word mikro/filmograf/iya, the two lexemes are "film" and "graph." The prefix "micro-" in borrowed compound words signifies very small or minute. The morpheme -iya in this word also forms a noun.

In the word mineralograf/iya, the two lexemes are "mineral" and "graph," with -iya forming a noun.

In the word okeanograf/ik, the two lexemes are "ocean" and "graph," and -ik forms an adjective. The structure of okeanograf/iya is similar, with -iya forming a noun.

In the word oksidoreduktaza/lar, the two lexemes are "oxidase" and "reductase," and -lar indicates plurality.

In the word poligonometr/iya, the two lexemes are "polygon" and "meter," with -iya forming a noun.

In the word pressoretsept/or/lar, the two lexemes are "press" and "receptor." The morpheme -or forms a noun, and -lar adds plurality. The word "press" in Uzbek means pressure, while "receptor" signifies something that receives. Adding the morpheme -or gives the word the meaning of a receiver.

The word radio/meteorograf contains the two lexemes "meteor" and "graph," both of which can be used independently in Uzbek. The addition of the prefix "radio-" indicates a connection to radio.

The word radio/spektrometr consists of the two lexemes "spectrum" and "meter." In Uzbek, "spectrum" can mean: a) the complete set of values of a certain quantity characterizing a particular system or process; b) the array of colored lines produced when complex light passes through a refracting medium such as a glass prism. We have already discussed the lexeme "meter." The addition of the prefix "radio-" also indicates a connection to radio.

The word rentgenograf/ik consists of the two lexemes "X-ray" and "graph," both of which can be used independently in Uzbek. The morpheme -ik forms an adjective. The structure of rentgenograf/iya is similar, with the morpheme -iya forming a noun.

The word spektrobolo/metr consists of three lexemes: "spectrum," "bolo," and "meter." We have discussed "spectrum" and "meter." The word "bolo," borrowed from Persian, means top, high, or height.

The word spektrogelioskop consists of the two lexemes "spectrum" and "helioscope." We have discussed "spectrum." The word "helioscope" means an instrument that allows observation of the sun's surface with the naked eye.

The word spektrograf/iya consists of the two lexemes "spectrum" and "graph." The morpheme -iya forms a noun. The structure of spektrogramma is similar, with "gramma" indicating a connection to writing.

The word **spektrokolorimetr** consists of the two lexemes "spectrum" and "colorimeter," both of which can be used independently in Uzbek. The word "colorimeter," borrowed from another language, is composed of "color" and "meter," meaning to measure. In Uzbek, it is used as a simple word. We have already discussed the "spectrum" part.

The word **spektrometr/iya** consists of the two lexemes "spectrum" and "meter." The morpheme **-iya** forms a noun.

The word **stereo/rentgenograf/iya** consists of the two lexemes "X-ray" and "graph," which we have discussed in detail. The prefix "stereo-" in borrowed compound words indicates meanings like solid, firm, volumetric, or spatial distribution.

In summary, these examples illustrate the presence and function of the "o" infix in Uzbek words, showing how borrowed elements are integrated into the language and how morphemes like -ik and -iya serve to form adjectives and nouns, respectively.

We've discussed the components of the word tele/rentgenograf/iya previously. The prefix "tele-" in borrowed compound words implies actions performed from a distance or related to television. The morpheme -iya forms a noun in this word.

For the word tele/rentgenoterapiya, the lexemes "tele-" and "X-ray" (rentgen) have been covered earlier. The word "therapy" can be used independently in Uzbek.

The word video/magnitofon comprises the lexemes "magnet" and "sound" (fon). "Fon" can be used independently in Uzbek to mean "sound," as can "magnet." The prefix "video-" in this word indicates that it is related to transmitting images via electronic signals.

In the word yodobromid, the two lexemes "iodine" (yod) and "bromide" are chemical substances in Uzbek.

In the word yodometr/ik, the two lexemes are "iodine" (yod) and "meter" (metr). The morpheme -ik forms an adjective in this word. The structure of yodometr/iya is similar, with the morpheme -iya forming a noun.

The word **shlakobeton** comprises the lexemes "slag" (shlak) and "concrete" (beton). "Shlak" in Uzbek refers to a glassy or stony substance left after extracting metal from ore, and "beton" is a mixture of cement and sand. The structure of **shlakoblok** is similar, with "block" (blok) as the second lexeme. This word means a product made from a mixture of slag and cement.

These examples demonstrate how different prefixes and morphemes contribute to the formation of adjectives and nouns in Uzbek, especially in the context of borrowed compound words.

2. The "infix" o that comes between the morpheme and lexeme.

We have previously discussed the components of the word astro/spectrograph/ic in detail. The "infix" appears between the prefix spectro- and the lexeme graph, which is why this word belongs

to this group. The word astro/spectrography is analyzed in the same way. Here, the suffix -yia serves to form a noun from the base word.

In the word magnetocardiograph/yia, the first lexeme is magnet and the second lexeme is graph. The part cardio- comes from borrowed words and indicates that the word is related to the heart. The suffix -yia functions to form a noun from the base part.

We have previously discussed the components spectro-, photo-, and meter in the word spectrophotometric. The suffix -ic in this word also serves to form an adjective. The composition of the word spectrophotometry is similar, with the suffix -yia serving to form a noun.

We have also discussed the components of the word spectrogelio/graph. The composition of the word spectrogelio/gramma is similar, with the word gramma coming from borrowed words, indicating its relation to writing.

We have previously discussed the components spectro- and meter in the word spectrogeometers. The part gonio- comes from borrowed words and indicates that it relates to angles.

In the word spectroisometric, the components spectro- and meter have been discussed earlier. The morpheme iso- comes from borrowed compound words and signifies equality and similarity in function.

In the word astro/spectrophotometric/yia, we have previously discussed the prefix astro-. The prefix spectro- is a component of borrowed compound words, indicating meanings such as vision, observation, and viewing. We have also discussed the prefix photo-. In this word, the base part is meter, and the suffix -yia functions to form a noun from the base word.

3. The "infix" o that appears in borrowed compound words which do not occur independently.

In the word *gigantopithecus*, the lexeme *gigant* can be used independently in Uzbek. The part *pithecus* comes from the Greek *pithekos* meaning "monkey." This part cannot be used independently in Uzbek and is encountered only within borrowed words, such as *Pithecanthropus* and *Australopithecus*.

In the word *interoreceptor/s*, the part *inter* comes from borrowed words and indicates meanings such as "international" or "between two connections." However, it does not have a distinct meaning on its own in Uzbek. The component *receptor* means "received thing." The morpheme *-or* is used in Uzbek to form personal nouns and can be seen in words like *acceptors* and *buyers*. The morpheme *-lar* adds the plural meaning to the word.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this issue has not yet been studied in Uzbek linguistics. There is no definitive opinion on the decomposition of such words in any source we have seen. However, it can be inferred from this article that solutions to the issue can be found by analyzing these words in parallel with other similar words (such as *sunflower* and *thousand-head*).

REFERENCES:

1. Berdialiyev A., Ermatov I. *Current Uzbek Literary Language*. – Tashkent: Tamaddun, 2022. – p. 121.
2. Khojiyev A. *Form Formation in Modern Uzbek Language*. – Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 1979. – p. 80.
3. Khojiyev A. *The System of Word Formation in Uzbek Language*. – Tashkent: O'qituvchi, 2007. – p. 168.

4. Mengliyev B., Kholiyorov O'. *Universal Guide to Uzbek Language*. – Tashkent: Fan, 2008. – p. 436.
5. Mengliyev B. et al. *Uzbek Language Word Formation Glossary*. – Tashkent: 2007. – p. 142.
6. Mahmudov N. *Uzbek Language Spelling Dictionary*. – Tashkent: Akademnashr, 2013. – p. 528.
7. Sapaev Q. *Current Uzbek Language*. – Tashkent: 2009. – p. 254.
8. Tojiev Y. *Morphemics of Uzbek Language*. – Tashkent: 1992. – p. 68.
9. Uzbekistan SSR Academy of Sciences. *Grammar of the Uzbek Language*. – Tashkent: Fan, 1973. – p. 609.
10. Nosirjon o'g'li, Khabibullayev Nodirbek. "Analysis of Some Words Which Are Difficult to Distribute into Uzbek Language." *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence* 4.03 (2024): 592-594.
11. Khabibullayev, Nodirbek. "Analysis of Some Words Whose Decomposition is Complex in Uzbek Language." *Journal of Education and Development* 3 (2024): 110-114.
12. Khabibullayev, Nodirbek Nosirjon o'g'li. "Comparison of Modal Words in Kazakh and Uzbek Languages." *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, Educational, Natural and Social Sciences* 3.5 (2023): 27-33.